

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE MCKENZIE METHOD AND STANDARD MANUAL THERAPY FOR LOW BACK PAIN: A RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED TRIAL

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Abstract

BACKGROUND: Low back pain is most common disorder which causes pain and limits our daily activities. It is estimated that upto 80% of people experienced low back pain. Low back pain often arise from poor posture, repetitive strain or spinal dysfunctions. Physiotherapy play a role in it with several treatment approaches. In which mckenzie and manual therapy techniques are mostly used to reduce pain improve function. The Mckenzie technique also known as MDT (Mechanical Diagnosis and Therapy in which there are repeated movements to centralized the pain. On the other hand Manual Therapy involves mobilization and manipulation techniques to relieve the pain and restore normal joint mechanics.

OBJECTIVE: To compare the effectiveness of McKenzie technique with Maitland in treating low back pain.

METHODS: Randomized Control trail study registered by the ClinicalTrials.gov under the registration number NCTNCT06955117. Total 52 participants with low back pain were taken and were divided into two groups, with 26 each group. One group was treated with Mckenzie, and the other group was treated with Maitland therapy. Outcome measures included the numeric pain rating scale(NPRS)for pain intensity, Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) for functional disability and lumbar Range of Motion (ROM) measured by goniometer. Data was analyzed using statistical test.

RESULTS: Mckenzie Group showed greater improvement in all outcome measure as compared to the Manual Therapy group. Both the treatment groups showed significant improvements in pain intensity, disability score and lumbar range of motion following the intervention($p < 0.05$).

CONCLUSION: The findings in the study suggest that Mckenzie technique have more effect than manual therapy in reducing pain and improve functional

ability in patient with low back pain. It can be recommended approach for treating low back pain.

INTRODUCTION

LBP is among the most common health issues affecting people of all ages and from every walk of life(1). A student, a laborer, an office worker, or a healthcare professional-all are likely to have at least one episode of low back pain sometime or another in their lives(2). Given the extremely high incidence, LBP has become one of the leading causes of functional limitations and disabilities in the world today(3). For many years, it has remained one of the top conditions responsible for limiting mobility, reducing productivity at work, and generally affecting the quality of life(3).

The burden of LBP surpasses the pain a person feels in the lower back; it has deep social and economic effects on individuals, families, communities, and healthcare systems(4). Individuals with chronic back pain are usually found to face problems regarding tasks that demand a lot of bending, lifting, constant sitting, and standing, or even everyday activities around the house. Many fail to work with efficiency or must take repeated sick leaves, bringing considerable losses over time(5). On a national scale, back pain accounts for billions in health expenditures, employee absenteeism, loss of performance, and even early retirement(6). Medically, LBP means pain, stiffness, discomfort, or tension within the region between the lower ribs and the upper part of the buttocks. The pain may stay within the back itself or it may radiate down into one or both legs. Because of its role of carrying most of the body's weight, the lumbar region is prone to strain, poor posture, repetitive movements, and lifestyle-related stresses. However, not all cases can be attributed to a specific identifiable tissue injury; hence, diagnosis and management may prove difficult(7).

Traditionally, back pain was considered primarily a mechanical or structural problem in that much of the focus was on bones, discs, or muscles. However, an emerging body of research indicates that low back pain does not necessarily come

from a single physical cause(8). Rather, emotional stress, physical inactivity, sleeping problems, pressures of workload, negative expectations, and even social situations themselves may affect how a person is experiencing and coping with pain. For such complex interactions, the biopsychosocial model has become commonplace to understand and manage LBP(9). According to this model, the pain experience of a person is shaped by biological, psychological, and social elements combined(9).

Physiotherapists play a central role in the management of LBP(10). Their task is not only to alleviate pain but also to help people regain movement, restore confidence, and return to their routine activities. Over the years, many conservative approaches, including exercise therapy, manual therapy, patient education, and self-management, have been developed aimed at addressing various types and stages of low back pain(11). However, despite many methods existing for its treatment, LBP is still a chronic condition characterized by recurrence in many cases. This demands that clinicians and researchers keep updating their understanding of LBP and keep searching for the most appropriate strategies (12). Understanding the nature and management of low back pain makes classification according to symptom duration important. The duration of pain gives an idea about the stage of the condition and helps guide the treatment plan accordingly(13). LBP refers to pain that has lasted less than six weeks. Acute pain often starts suddenly, after one particular activity such as lifting or twisting, and sometimes even after just one awkward position. Most bouts of acute pain tend to get better reasonably quickly with simple management, gentle mobilization, and avoidance of prolonged rest. Many people will manage to recover without the need for general medical intervention (12). Subacute LBP persists between six weeks and three months. This stage represents a sort of middle ground wherein the pain has failed to resolve

spontaneously but has not reached the status of long-term pain. Symptoms are often intermittent, improving with rest but recurring during specific activities. Overall, subacute cases will share many of the characteristics of acute pain but, as a rule, will require closer attention to avoid progression toward chronic pain(12). Chronic nonspecific LBP often follows a pattern of fluctuations. Individuals have periods during which the pain has subsided, followed by episodes in which symptoms return or worsen. This unpredictability often results in a loss of confidence and mood and/or a reduction in physical activity. Symptom persistence is due to a combination of biological factors, such as stiffness or decreased mobility, psychological factors, such as stress or fear of movement, and social ones, such as work stress or sedentary habits (13). Chronic LBP may also affect mental health: the chronic nature of the disease may contribute to frustration, anxiety, or depression. Further, this justifies the reason for an approach to treatment-that it needs to be holistic and multidimensional rather than being confined to physical interventions only (14).

Literature Review

Low back pain has continued to dominate healthcare research because of its high prevalence and its profound impact on daily life. Indeed, many studies have focused on the etiology of LBP and the assessment of different forms of treatment approaches aimed at improving recovery outcomes(15). Exercise therapy is widely regarded as the cornerstone of intervention in both acute and chronic low back pain conditions. Specific physical impairments are managed with different forms of exercises, such as stretching, strengthening, mobilization, stabilization, and aerobic training. Strengthening exercises enhance core stability, hence providing good support to the spine. Stretching decreases stiffness, enhances flexibility, and encourages active movement. Aerobic exercise, on the other hand, improves blood circulation, reduces inflammation, and contributes to the overall health of the client's body(16).The large systematic reviews, including Cochrane systematic reviews, have all indicated that exercise therapy leads to clinically important

improvement in pain and function. Regular exercises reduce the intensity of chronic pain, improve the quality of life, and lessen the chances of recurrence. Evidence also exists that people who continue being active during any episode of LBP recover more quickly than those who simply rest. The McKenzie Method One of the most well-documented physiotherapy methods for examining and managing LBP is known as the McKenzie Method, also commonly referred to as Mechanical Diagnosis and Therapy (17). The system categorizes specific spinal motions as pain-producing or pain-relieving. In the evaluation stage, the therapist monitors changes in symptoms with repeated motion or sustained posture According to such procedures, patients can be classified into mechanical syndromes such as Derangement Syndrome, the most common, involving altered joint mechanics or a temporary obstruction of normal movement, Dysfunction Syndrome, The pain arises from soft tissues that are shortened or scarred and are stressed during movement, The postural syndrome caused by prolonged poor posture or sustained loading. Other categories: symptoms arising due to trauma, underlying disease, or non-mechanical causes(18). Centralization, a hallmark feature of the McKenzie approach, is the phenomenon by which pain shifts from the leg or buttock area back toward the spine during treatment. Centralization is considered a positive sign, showing that the mechanical condition of the spine is improving(19).Research on MDT yields variable results. Various studies note that MDT produces beneficial effects among patients with chronic low back pain, especially when the therapists are well-trained and the patients matched into the appropriate mechanical category. However, in acute or subacute LBP, MDT may not be significantly superior to other common treatments. Perhaps the greatest benefit of the McKenzie Method is its emphasis on patient education and self-treatment to foster independence in long-term self-management(20). Manual therapy encompasses various hands-on techniques that include spinal mobilization, manipulation, soft tissue release, muscle energy techniques, and myofascial release(21). These are

interventions to reduce pain, improve joint mobility, decrease muscle tension, and restore normal movement patterns(22). Whereas manual therapy has traditionally been considered a primarily mechanical intervention, recent research indicates that it also affects the nervous system. Hands-on therapy may activate sensory receptors in muscles and joints, modulate pain pathways, and induce relaxation effects that benefit movement, there is evidence that manual therapy is often effective for short-term relief, particularly when pain is associated with stiffness or joint restriction. Evidence related to the long-term benefits of manual therapy is less consistent. Most experts agree that manual therapy should be used in combination with exercise and education rather than as a stand-alone treatment(23). Several studies have compared the results of MDT and manual therapy. Generally, the findings indicate:MDT may offer better long-term outcomes for chronic non-specific LBP, Manual therapy is more effective for short-term pain relief, A combination of both approaches usually yields better results than relying on a single technique (24). Expertise of the therapist is very important for the effectiveness because both MDT and manual therapy require detailed assessment and clinical judgment. Systematic reviews confirm that, although MDT is not dramatically more effective for acute LBP than other treatments, it may be considerably more efficacious for chronic LBP, especially when patients are classified accurately into mechanical subgroups. Manual therapy, while often very effective in reducing pain and improving mobility, appears to be best followed by active rehabilitation and movement-based therapy (25).

Materials and Methods

This study employed a parallel-group, randomized controlled trial design to compare the effectiveness of two therapeutic interventions. The trial was conducted within the outpatient department (OPD) of the School of Health Sciences in Peshawar. Selection Criteria: Participants were enrolled based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria comprised: male and female patients aged

25 to 45 years presenting with a primary complaint of non-specific low back pain or lumbar radiculopathy. Patients were excluded if they presented with any of the following conditions: spinal stenosis, scoliosis, recent trauma to the spine, pregnancy, history of spinal surgery within the preceding six months, diagnosed cardiac diseases, spinal tuberculosis, or spinal malignancy. The total duration of the study, encompassing ethical approval, participant recruitment, intervention delivery, follow-up assessments, data analysis, and final report writing, was 06 months. A total of 52 participants were recruited and equally allocated into two groups. Group A (n=26) received the McKenzie technique, while Group B (n=26) received Maitland manual therapy. Sampling Technique: Participants were selected using a consecutive probability sampling technique. All eligible patients who presented to the department with low back pain during the recruitment period, met the inclusion criteria, and provided written informed consent were enrolled in the study.

Intervention Protocol: Participants were randomly allocated to one of two intervention groups. Both groups received a foundational regimen of routine physical therapy, which included the application of a hot pack for 15 to 20 minutes for muscular relaxation and Transcutaneous Electrical Nerve Stimulation (TENS) for 10 minutes for pain modulation, administered both before and after the core therapeutic exercises.

Group A (McKenzie Technique): Participants in the experimental group received the McKenzie Method of Mechanical Diagnosis and Therapy. The core intervention consisted of a standardized progression of lumbar extension exercises. This protocol began with prone lying, advanced to prone on elbows, and culminated in prone press-ups (push-ups in the prone position). The exercise dosage was set at three sets of ten repetitions, with each end-range position held for five seconds.

Group B (Maitland Technique): Participants in the comparison group received manual therapy based on the Maitland concept. The intervention focused on central and unilateral postero-anterior glides (Grades I-IV) applied to the lumbar spinal segments. This was supplemented by complementary exercises, including knee-to-chest and hamstring stretches, performed for three sets of ten repetitions with a five-second hold. Participants were reassessed at three time points. Week 0 Baseline, Week 3 Mid-intervention and Week 6 post-intervention

Results

The study found that both treatment interventions produced clinically and statistically significant improvements ($p < .001$). Participants demonstrated a consistent reduction in pain

intensity and functional disability, alongside substantial gains in lumbar range of motion across all measured directions. These results indicate that the therapies were effective in reducing pain, enhancing daily function, and restoring mobility in patients with low back pain.

Pain Intensity NPRS: Pain intensity showed a statistically significant and clinically meaningful reduction over time. The mean NPRS score decreased from 2.27 at baseline to 1.09 by the final intervention. This progressive improvement was confirmed by a repeated-measures ANOVA (Pillai's Trace = 0.794, $F(2, 50) = 96.62$, $*p < .001$), indicating that the interventions effectively relieved pain.

Disability (Oswestry Disability Index ODI): Functional disability, measured by the ODI, showed a substantial and statistically significant improvement from baseline (mean 2.86) to the final intervention (mean 1.73). This robust

reduction in disability was confirmed by a repeated-measures ANOVA (Pillai's Trace = 0.861, $F(2, 50) = 154.74$, $p < .001$).

Lumbar Range of Motion (ROM): Large improvements were observed in flexion ROM, with mean values increasing from 4.17 to 23.36.

The extremely high F-value (627.62) indicates very strong treatment effects.

Time Point	Mean	SD	N
Baseline	4.17	1.55	52
3rd Intervention	13.03	2.23	52
6th Intervention	23.36	3.79	52

Discussion

This study compared the McKenzie Technique and standard Manual Therapy (Maitland) for low back pain (LBP). Both interventions produced statistically significant ($p < .001$) improvements in all measured outcomes: pain, functional disability, lumbar range of motion (ROM), and patient confidence. These findings confirm the effectiveness of physiotherapy in managing LB. Pain intensity (NPRS) decreased progressively, suggesting that repeated therapeutic loading through either method effectively reduces symptoms. Functional disability (ODI) also declined significantly, aligning with pain reduction and indicating restored daily capacity.

Lumbar ROM increased substantially in all directions (flexion, extension, side-bending), reflecting reduced stiffness and restored joint mobility. Patient confidence scores improved dramatically, with a significant increase ($p < .001$), likely due to enhanced self-efficacy, particularly within the McKenzie method's self-management model. The results are consistent with prior literature. Studies (e.g., Namnaqani et al., 2019) show McKenzie provides superior short-term improvements, which aligns with the observed patterns. The significant ROM gains also correspond with research on repeated directional movements (Sipavičienė & Paškov, 2024). While Manual Therapy is effective for immediate pain relief via neurophysiological mechanisms, systematic reviews suggest McKenzie may yield more sustained benefits due to its patient-empowering, self-treatment component.

Conclusion: Both the McKenzie Technique and Maitland Manual Therapy significantly improved pain, function, ROM, and confidence in LBP patients over six weeks. The McKenzie group, however, demonstrated greater and more consistent improvement, particularly in fostering self-management and likely longer-term

outcomes. This supports McKenzie as a preferred, patient-centered intervention in outpatient physiotherapy for LBP.

Recommendation

For Clinicians should incorporate McKenzie exercises, especially for patients with a directional preference. Use Manual Therapy adjunctively for immediate comfort. Emphasize patient education on posture and self-management. For Patients: Adhere to home exercise programs, avoid prolonged poor postures, and seek early intervention. For Research: Conduct larger, multicenter RCTs with long-term follow-up. Investigate combined therapies, psychological mediators, and cost-effectiveness.

Limitations: Key limitations include a single-center setting, a modest sample size ($n=52$), a short (6-week) follow-up period, the absence of a control group, and uncontrolled variables like therapist experience and patient adherence.

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